

**A SYSTEMATIC OBSERVATION OF EXECUTION OF APPROACHES TO TEACHING ENGLISH AT
SECONDARY LEVEL**

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Introduction:

Education is that equipment which can properly mould the shape of human beings. While leading the life many difficulties are faced by man. These difficulties enable man to find the solutions through day to day experiences. Once man is able to solve the difficulties, he can change his behaviour and change in behaviour means education. As education is continuous and comprehensive process in the same way to experience throughout the life is of the same importance. Experience is a natural process of education. The education which is earned through experience is called formal education.

In informal education teaching and learning processes are very important. For this teacher and learner both factors are equally important. Teacher is the enlightened person who enriches learners by providing all type of knowledge, which makes the learner intellectually, emotionally, socially, spiritually and physically developed. The work of teacher is not limited around providing bookish knowledge to learner but the ideal teacher always tries to give something new and innovative to his students. The teacher who transforms the behavioural character of the students is the best teacher.

So in today's modern teaching process the following fundamentals are to be pressed more:

- 1) Emphasis on learner
- 2) Guidance for learner
- 3) Development of learner

In the process of teaching and learning it is language which plays a very vital role. The best teacher is that who has a good command over language with its powerful weapon of command over language. The teacher can impress the students. Language is the most important aspect for those who want to do their career in speaking because a good speaker can attract a large number of audiences if he has a good treasure of language. Language is the key factor in gaining any type of knowledge. As we observe the curriculum we can notice that language was taught by memorizing grammatical rules and by translating passages from the second language

to the first language and vice versa. Till 19th century this was considered as a standard method of teaching language every grammatical rule which was contained in chapter was practiced with a lot of written practices.

As we focused on methods of teaching which are the combinations of techniques and followed by the teachers for the improvement of students then we understand that approaches are the techniques which mould the teaching content in interesting way. Methods and approaches are helpful to make a base of students. Approaches are theoretical view which defines language very well. When we think about methods and approaches, its need of time to examine the implementation of approaches while implementing which difficulties are faced by the teachers along with this we have to check the effectiveness of approaches as compare to traditional methods. If the teaching content is not understood by the students, expected result will not be proved. So its need of time to mould teaching content up to the understandable level of the students.

According to Asher and James (1982) approaches are the philosophies of teacher about language teaching that can be applied in the classroom by using different techniques of language teaching. As the approaches are used to teaching language means one can understand the meaning, functions as well as the uses of language.

In the teaching field many changes are occurred so we have to check in the modern techniques of teaching how the students respond to the techniques. In present research by comparing the traditional method and new approaches to teaching English researcher has done the research on implementation of approaches to teaching English at secondary level.

Objectives:

1. To compare the implementation of approaches in Marathi medium school and English Medium School.

Hypothesis:

H1

There is no significant difference between the mean scores of pre and post test of experimental group of 9th Standard English subject in comprehensive test on unit structural approach applied in English medium schools.

H2

There is no significant difference between the mean scores of pre test and post test of experimental group of 9th Standard English subject in comprehensive test on unit structural approach applied in Marathi medium schools.

H3

There is no significant difference between the mean scores of pre and post test of experimental group of 9th Standard English subject in comprehensive test on unit constructivist approach applied in English Medium School.

H4

There is no significant difference between the mean scores of pre and post test of experimental group of 9th Standard English subject in comprehensive test on unit constructivist approach applied in Marathi medium school.

Method of Research:

Researcher has used experimental method for this research. To study the achievement of students by using the structural and constructivist approaches researcher has used experimental method.

Sample for Research:

Sr. No.	Medium of School	Students		Total Population	Sample	Percentage (%)
		Boys	Girls			
1	English	399	286	685	250	36.49%
2	Marathi	28671	24644	53315	250	0.46%

As per the above objective to study and compare the achievement of 500 students by using the structural and constructivist approaches to teaching English of Marathi medium and English medium schools of standard 9th were chosen as sample for experimental method. Sampling procedure is used to select the students.

Analysis of Data:

Objective is to compare the implementation of approaches in Marathi medium schools and English medium schools.

Null Hypothesis Ho1

There is no significant difference between the mean scores of pre and post test of experimental group of 9th Standard English students in comprehensive test applied in English medium school on unit structural approach.

Table No. 1

Means, SD and t ratio of Pre- test and post -test op experimental group for the unit Structural approach applied in English medium schools.

Sr. No.	Particulars	N	Mean	SD	calculated t	Table t		Df	Result
						0.01	0.05		
1	Pre Test	250	1.20	3.24	5.801	2.59	1.96	498	Rejected
2	Post Test	250	1.96	1.3					

Observation and Interpretation

The table number 1 shows that the test applied to the pre-test and post-test scores obtained by the students of experimental group the Mean and SD value of the protest is 1.20 and 3.24 respectively and Mean and SD value of post-test is 1.96 and 1.3 respectively

Table also shows the degree of freedom calculated t i.e. 5.801 is greater than table value i.e. 2.59. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.01 level of significance.

Null hypothesis Ho2

There is no significant difference between the Mean scores of pre and post-test of experimental group of 9th Standard English students in comprehensive test applied in Marathi medium school on unit Structural approach.

Table No. 2

Means, SD and t ratio of Pre- test and Post -test op experimental group for the unit Structural approach applied in Marathi medium school.

Sr. No.	Particulars	N	Mean	SD	calculated t	Table t		Df	Result
						0.01	0.05		
1	pre test	250	1.22	2.91	5.397	2.59	1.96	498	Rejected
2	post test	250	1.92	1.46					

Observation and Interpretation

The table number 2 shows that the test applied to the pre-test and post -test scores obtained by the students of experimental group the Mean and SD value of the protest is 1.22 and 2.91 respectively and Mean and SD value of post- test is 1.92 and 1.46 respectively

Table also shows the degree of freedom calculated t i.e. 5.397 is greater than table value i.e. 2.59. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.01 level of significance.

Null Hypothesis Ho3

There is no significant difference between the mean scores of pre and post test of experimental group of 9th standard English students in comprehensive test applied in English medium schools on unit constructivist approach.

Table No. 3

Means, SD and t ratio of Pre test and post test op experimental group for the unit constructivist approach applied in English Medium schools.

Sr. No.	particulars	N	Mean	SD	Calculated t	Table t		Df	Result
						0.01	0.05		
1	pre test	250	1.24	2.78	5.701	2.59	1.96	498	Rejected
2	post test	250	1.89	0.5					

Observation and Interpretation

the table number 3 shows that the test applied to the pre-test and post-test scores obtained by the students of experimental group the Mean and SD value of the protest is 1.24 and 2.78 respectively and Mean and SD value of post test is 1.89 and 0.5 respectively

Table also shows the degree of freedom calculated t i.e. 5.701 is greater than table value i.e. 2.59. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.01 level of significance.

Null Hypothesis H_04

There is no significant difference between the Mean scores of pre and post-test of experimental group of 9th standard English students in comprehensive test applied in Marathi medium schools on unit constructivist approach.

Table No. 4

Means, SD and t ratio of Pre-test and post- test op experimental group for the unit constructivist approach applied in Marathi medium school.

Sr. No.	Particulars	N	Mean	SD	Calculated t	Table t		Df	Result
						0.01	0.05		
1	pre test	250	1.13	2.5	5.294	2.59	1.96	498	Rejected
2	post test	250	1.76	1.05					

Observation and Interpretation

The table number 4 shows that the test applied to the pre-test and post -test scores obtained by the students of experimental group the Mean and SD value of the protest is 1.13 and 2.5 respectively and mean and SD value of post test is 1.76 and 1.05 respectively

Table also shows the degree of freedom calculated t i.e. 5.294 is greater than table value i.e. 2.59. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.01 level of significance.

Major Findings

Result related to the pre-test and post-test of experimental group

Sr. No.	Hypothesis	't' Value	Level of significance	Result
1	There is no significant difference between the mean scores of pre and post test of experimental group of 9 th standard English students in comprehensive test applied in English medium school on unit structural approach	5.801	0.01	Rejected
2	There is no significant difference between the mean scores of pre and post test of experimental group of 9 th standard English students in comprehensive test applied in Marathi medium school on unit structural	5.397	0.01	Rejected

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	approach.			
3	There is no significant difference between the mean scores of pre and post test of experimental group of 9 th standard English students in comprehensive test applied in English medium schools on unit constructivist approach.	5.701	0.01	Rejected
4	There is no significant difference between the mean scores of pre and post test of experimental group of 9 th standard English students in comprehensive test applied in Marathi medium schools on unit constructivist approach.	5.294	0.01	Rejected

1. Results of the study have proved that structural approach applied in English medium schools as well as Marathi medium schools are more effective than traditional method of teaching English at secondary level.
2. The results of the study have proved that constructivist approach applied in English medium schools as well as Marathi medium schools are more effective than traditional methods of teaching English at secondary level.
3. The results of structural approach of the students of both Marathi and English medium were the same one.
4. The results of constructivist approach of the students of both schools in rural area and urban area were the same.

Conclusion

This paper has studied a comparative study of implementation of approaches to teaching English at secondary level. It proved that both the approaches are more effective than the traditional method in English medium schools as well as in English medium schools. The results of structural and constructivist approaches in both English and Marathi medium schools were the same.

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